

DMP for the CEELOMLOE project (PID2023-150590OB-I00)

Version 1

Description

This DMP includes data from the project titled "Special education schools under the LOMLOE paradigm: their transformation into support centers for ordinary schools and proposals for the education of students who require specialized supports" (CEELOMLOE in its Spanish acronym).

This research project aims to provide scientific evidence contributing to the progressive transformation of Special Education (SPED) schools in Spain, aligning with the new roles assigned by the additional fourth provision of the LOMLOE (the educational law that regulates the Spanish educational system).

The additional fourth provision of the LOMLOE stipulates that, within ten years from its approval in 2020, SPED schools would be dedicated exclusively to the schooling of students requiring highly specialized attention, while also serving as reference and support centers for regular schools.

In this context, three years after the approval of the LOMLOE, we propose a project to analyze the current level of transformation in SPED schools achieved by this law and we propose guidelines for ensuring that the transformation of SPED schools is carried out while truly respecting the principles of inclusive education.

In the project, we will generate five types of data:

1. Geographic location of SPED schools.

One of the project's objectives is to analyze which areas of towns and cities have SPED schools and whether there are different criteria for locating SPED schools and mainstream schools.

In towns with fewer than 100,000 inhabitants that have at least one SPED school, we will calculate the Manhattan distance between each school and the town hall. We will provide this data in spreadsheets.

In towns with more than 100,000 inhabitants that have at least one SPED school, we will present an image file representing the city map with the location of these SPED schools.

This analysis will be conducted for all SPED schools in the Valencian Community (a region in eastern Spain with approximately 5.5 million inhabitants).

Both types of data will be stored in Zenodo.

2. Evolution of the number of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools.

Another objective of the project will be to analyze whether, in recent decades, there has been an evolution in the number of SPED schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools across the Spanish education system as a whole.

The analysis will be conducted for the period 2001-2024.

Data will be analyzed for Spain as a whole and for each of the 17 autonomous communities and the autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla.

The school's ownership (public, private, or private-subsidized) will be included as an analysis variable.

The data will be presented in data sheets stored in Zenodo.

3. Interviews with professionals.

Another objective is to understand the perceptions of SPED schools professionals about how the publication of the additional fourth provision of the LOMLOE has affected the functioning of their schools so far. To this end, we will interview teachers, educators, counselors, and members of SPED schools management teams from the autonomous communities of Catalonia, the Balearic Islands, the Principality of Asturias, and the Valencian Community.

The interviews will be transcribed using Gladia software and stored in Zenodo as text files.

All interviews will be anonymized. Only the interviewee's autonomous community of origin and professional role will be reported.

4. Interviews with families.

Additionally, we will also conduct interviews with family members of students enrolled in SPED schools regarding their assessment of the proposals of the Additional Fourth Provision of the LOMLOE and their evaluation of the educational support their children receive in the SPED schools where they are enrolled. Specifically, we will ask about their impressions regarding academic performance, improvements in autonomy, and attention to students' emotional development provided in the SPED schools, as well as job prospects after completing their SPED education.

The interviews will be transcribed using Gladia software and stored in Zenodo as text files.

All interviews will be anonymized. Only the interviewee's autonomous community of origin will be reported.

5. Questionnaires for professionals.

Based on the results of the interviews with professionals, we will develop a questionnaire to assess the perceptions of SPED schools professionals regarding the two functions that the fourth additional provision of the LOMLOE assigns to these schools: providing education to students who require highly specialized attention and acting as reference and support centers for mainstream schools.

This questionnaire will be administered to a broad sample of professionals.

The responses will be coded in datasheets.

The datasheets will be stored in Zenodo.

Funder

MCIU/AEI and FEDER, UE

Grant

Special education schools
under the LOMLOE paradigm:
PID2023-150590OB-I00

Researchers

Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez, Pilar Sanz-Cervera

Organizations
Universidad de Valencia

1. Basic Information

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In towns with more than 100,000 inhabitants that have at least one SPED school, we will present an image file representing the city map with the location of these SPED schools.

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Both types of data will be stored in Zenodo.

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The analysis will be conducted for the period 2001-2024.

Data will be analyzed for Spain as a whole and for each of the 17 autonomous communities and the autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla.

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This questionnaire will be administered to a broad sample of professionals.

The responses will be coded in datasheets.

The datasheets will be stored in Zenodo.

Researchers:

Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

Pilar Sanz-Cervera

Affiliations:

Universidad de Valencia

Contact: Tárraga-Mínguez Raúl (raul.tarraga@uv.es), Sanz-Cervera Pilar (pilar.sanz-cervera@uv.es)

2. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

3. Funding

Funder: MCIU/AEI and FEDER, UE

Grant: Special education schools under the LOMLOE paradigm: PID2023-150590OB-I00

4. Generic Data Questions

Descriptions

CHIST-ERA Data Management - Generic Questions

This DMP includes data from the project titled "Special education schools under the LOMLOE paradigm: their transformation into support centers for ordinary schools and proposals for the education of students who require specialized supports" (CEELOMLOE in its Spanish acronym).

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management - Generic Questions](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Documentation And Data Quality

1.1 Documentation And Data Quality

1.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

1.1.1.1 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

All files will be stored in Zenodo.

Each data type will have a separate ID (provided by Zenodo).

There are 5 data types in this project.

The following describes how data files will be named for each of these types.

1. Geographic location of SPED schools.

1.1. Localities with fewer than 100,000 inhabitants:

A data sheet will be provided with the name of each school, its postal address, geographic coordinates, and the calculated Manhattan distance from this school to the local town hall.

This same information will be provided for the remaining schools in localities with at least one SPED school.

1.2. Localities with more than 100,000 inhabitants:

Four files will be provided with maps of Alicante, Castelló de la Plana, Elche, and Valencia, showing the locations of the SPED schools.

2. Evolution of the number of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools.

A data sheet will be provided showing the evolution of the number of SPED schools and SPED classrooms in mainstream schools from 2001 to 2024.

3. Interviews with professionals.

A text file will be provided for each interview.

The identity of the interviewees will be completely anonymized.

Each text file will be named according to the professional position held by the interviewee and a consecutive number.

The professional position codes will correspond to the Spanish word for the professional position.

These codes are:

- TUT: Tutor.
- OR: Educational Counselor.
- DIR: Member of the Management Team.
- ED: Special Education Educator.
- AL: Hearing and Language Teacher.
- EF: Physical Education Teacher.
- MUS: Music Teacher.
- FP: Vocational Training Teacher.
- FIS: Physiotherapist.

4. Interviews with Families.

A text file will be provided for each interview.

The identity of the interviewees will be completely anonymized.

Each text file will be named with the code of the Autonomous Community in which the interview is conducted and a consecutive number.

The codes are:

- AST: Principality of Asturias.
- BAL: Balearic Islands.
- CAT: Catalonia.
- VAL: Valencian Community.

5. Questionnaires for Professionals.

The results from the questionnaire will be presented in a data sheet.

The content of each item will appear in the first row.

The data will be fully anonymized.

1.1.1.3 Consider how this information will be captured and where it will be recorded

The five types of data generated by the project will be published on Zenodo in five separate registries.

The DOIs corresponding to these registries will be public and listed in the various project reports.

1.1.2 What data quality control measures will be used?

1.1.2.1 Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented

- Standardised data capture
- Data entry validation
- Peer review of data

Each type of data will follow different QA processes.

1. Geographic location of SPED schools.

Two researchers will independently collect information on the geographic coordinates of each school. Additionally, they will calculate the Manhattan distance from each school to the local town hall.

If there is discrepancy between the results of both researchers, a meeting will be held to clarify the reasons and to identify the correct data.

Once the information has been reviewed, the data will be uploaded to Zenodo.

2. Evolution of the number of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools.

Two researchers will independently collect information on the number of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools for the period analyzed.

If there is discrepancy, a meeting will be held to clarify the reasons and to identify the correct data.

Once the information has been reviewed, the data will be uploaded to Zenodo.

3. Interviews with professionals and (4) with families.

The interviews will be audio-recorded.

The audio recordings will be transcribed using Gladia.

Each transcript will be reviewed by a member of the research team.

The reviewed text files will be stored on a password-protected external hard drive held by the research team.

Once all the transcripts have been reviewed, the content will be uploaded to Zenodo.

5. Questionnaires for professionals.

The questionnaires will be completed using the Lime Survey tool.

Once all the responses have been collected, the data will be cleaned using the following procedures:

- a) Review of cases to eliminate responses that were completed in an unjustifiably low amount of time.
- b) Review of cases to eliminate rows with a higher than expected number of missing values.
- c) Analysis of maximum and minimum values for each quantitative variable.

2 Reused Data

3 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

3.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

3.1.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1.1 Describe where the data will be stored and backed up during research activities and how often the backup will be performed

disco.uv.es

per Week

The data generated by the project will be sent to at least one of the two principal investigators.

The principal investigators will meet weekly and will host the data collected during the last 7 days on disco.uv.es.

3.1.2 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

3.1.2.1 Explain who will have access to the data during the research and how access to data is controlled, especially in collaborative partnerships

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez (0000-0002-4458-5763)
- Pilar Sanz-Cervera (0000-0001-6919-6150)

Only the two principal investigators of the project will have access to the shared space on disco.uv.es

3.1.2.2 Explain which institutional data protection policies are in place

Universidad de Valencia

The University of Valencia (UV) establishes that data protection in research must comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (European Union) and the LOPDGDD (Spanish Data Protection Act), requiring the processing of personal data based on the principle of legitimacy and respecting the ARCO (Access, Rectification, Erasure, and Objection) rights of data subjects. The UV offers resources such as the Data Protection Office and the Electronic Office for compliance with regulations, the registration of processing activities, and the processing of complaints.

4 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

4.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

4.1.1 Personal data

4.1.1.1 Are there any personal data to be formulated?

No

4.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

4.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

4.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez (0000-0002-4458-5763)
- Pilar Sanz-Cervera (0000-0001-6919-6150)

4.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

The data generated by the project will be published openly on Zenodo.

4.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

4.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

The data will be published under license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0.

4.1.2.3 Third-party data restrictions

4.1.2.3.1 Are there any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data?

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

4.1.3 Ethical issues

4.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

- Ethical issues surrounding personal data
- Other

1. Geographic location of SPED schools.

The data will provide the geographic coordinates of the SPED schools and the rest of the schools in the municipality. This data is already public. The project will provide the data in a single document.

2. Interviews with professionals and (3) with families.

The transcripts will not include any personal or other data that could identify the interviewee.

4. Questionnaires for professionals.

The questionnaires will be anonymous, and the information obtained will be processed in an aggregated manner.

5 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

5.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

5.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

5.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

5.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

5.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

Each data block of the project (1. Geographic location of SPED schools; 2. Evolution of the number of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools; 3. Interviews with professionals; 4. Interviews with Families; and 5. Questionnaires for professionals) will be published in Zenodo once it has been obtained.

5.1.1.4 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

5.1.1.6 Indicate how the data will be used

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

5.1.1.7 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

5.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

5.1.2.1 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Other

The 5 types of data selected for conservation are:

1. Geographic location of SPED schools.

Geographic coordinates of all SPED schools in the Valencian Community and calculation of the Manhattan distance between these schools and the local town hall.

2. Evolution of the number of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools.

Data sheet showing the number and ownership (public, private, and private-subsidized) of special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools in Spain for the period 2001–2024.

3. Interviews with professionals.

Revised transcript of interviews.

4. Interviews with Families.

Revised transcript of interviews.

5. Questionnaires for professionals.

Questionnaire responses.

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

5.1.2.2 Indicate where the data will be deposited

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

5.1.2.3 How will the data be effectively curated beyond the lifetime of the grant

The deposit of data in Zenodo is done to guarantee its long-term preservation and its accessibility through the dois that the repository provides.

5.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

5.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

6 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

6.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

6.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

6.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

6.1.1.2 Explain the co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners

Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez and Pilar Sanz-Cervera will meet weekly to discuss the management of the data generated by the project over the past 7 days.

At the meeting, they will apply data quality assurance procedures and they will store the data on disco.uv.es.

Once data collection for each of the project's five data types is complete, Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez will retrieve the data from disco.uv.es. He will take the

necessary steps to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles, and he will store it on Zenodo.

6.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

6.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

6.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

5. Data Management

Descriptions

Manhattan distance between (special education) schools and towns' councils

The data refers to the Manhattan distance between the special education schools of the Valeniana Community (Spain) and the town councils of the towns in which these schools are located.

Only data referring to localities with less than 100,000 inhabitants are included.

The data referring to the largest localities is included in another Zenodo record in map format.

The calculations have been carried out with the Cartociudad tool:

<https://www.cartociudad.es/web/portal/herramientas-calculos/calculo-de-distancias>

The resulting file is the copy of all the independent files created by this tool.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Reuse of Existing Data

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

Secondary data

Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

We will collect geographic coordinate data for schools and high schools in all towns with fewer than 100,000 inhabitants in the Valencian Community (Spain) that have at least one special education school.

We will calculate the Manhattan distance from these schools to the town hall. To do this, we will use the Cartociudad tool:

<https://www.cartociudad.es/web/portal/herramientas-calculos/calculodedistancias>

These data will be stored on a single .xlsx file.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de facto standard in my discipline

The .xlsx format does not meet all the requirements to be considered open.

However, it is a widely accepted format used by researchers in multiple fields.

Furthermore, the Free Software Foundation considers it a pseudo-standard format, as it complies with the ISO standard.

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

KB (kilobyte)

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.2 Explain how data provenance will be documented

The provenance of the data will be reported through Zenodo's metadata fields.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

The entire dataset will be contained in a single .xlsx file.

The two researchers who will collect the data will use this single file independently.

This file will be designed by Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez.

The file will have as many pages as there are towns in the Valencian Community with at least one special education school.

The columns in the file will be those provided by the Cartociudad distance calculator.

(<https://www.cartociudad.es/web/portal/herramientas-calculos/calculodedistancias>)

2.1.1.4 Consider what other documentation is needed to enable re-use

The .xlsx file will be divided into different sheets.

Each sheet will contain data for a different location.

The first row of each column will contain the variable names.

The first columns will refer to the geographic coordinates of the schools.

The last columns will refer to the geographic coordinates of the city hall.

After that, the Manhattan distance between the two geographic points will appear.

3 Reused Data

4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident and describe the main risks and how these will be managed

The data will be stored on disco.uv.es, a password-protected digital file storage space provided by the University of Valencia.

The data generated throughout the project will be stored there weekly.

This storage space regularly creates copies of its contents, ensuring that the data can be recovered in the event of an incident.

No sensitive information is expected to be collected during this phase of the project. Only the postal addresses and geographic coordinates of the schools (information that is already public).

5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez
- Pilar Sanz-Cervera

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.2.3 Third-party data restrictions

5.1.2.3.1 Are there any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data?

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Other

The data will provide the geographic coordinates of the SPED schools and the rest of the schools in the municipality. This data is already public. The project will provide the data in a single document.

6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be published in Zenodo once the process of compiling and calculating the Manhattan distance between schools and city halls has been completed.

6.1.1.4 Indicate the expected timely release

2024-07-22

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.8 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Data will be preserved if:

- a) It can be useful to other researchers interested in the field.
- b) It allows for replication of the results of our project.
- c) It is technically possible to preserve it.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

6.1.2.4 Indicate where the data will be deposited

European Data Portal

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

6.1.2.5 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.2.6 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data.

No specific tools will be necessary to re-use the data.

6.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

Location on the map of special education schools in cities with more than 100,000 inhabitants

The maps represent the geographical position of the special education schools in the Valencian Community (Spain) and the town councils of the towns in which they are located.

Only data referring to localities with more than 100,000 inhabitants are included.

The data referring to the minor localities is included in another Zenodo record in database format.

To create the maps, the Leaflet library (Cheng et al., 2023) in R version 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2023) was used.

References:

Cheng, J., Schloerke, B., Karambelkar, B., Xie, & Y. (2023). Leaflet: Create interactive web maps with the JavaScript 'Leaflet' library (R package version 2.2.1). <https://CRAN.Rproject.org/package=leaflet>

R Core Team (2023). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing (version 4.3.2) [Computer software]. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Reuse of Existing Data

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

Secondary data

Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

The data is presented in html format.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de facto standard in my discipline

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

MB (megabyte)

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.2 Explain how data provenance will be documented

The provenance of the data will be reported through Zenodo's metadata fields.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

The data represents the location of special education schools on the map of their localities. Data is presented for localities in the Valencian Community with more than 100,000 inhabitants: Alicante, Castelló de la Plana, Elche, and Valencia.

Each HTML file will be named as the city whose data it contains.

3 Reused Data

4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident and describe the main risks and how these will be managed

The data will be stored on disco.uv.es, a password-protected digital file storage space provided by the University of Valencia.

The data generated throughout the project will be stored there weekly.

This storage space regularly creates copies of its contents, ensuring that the data can be recovered in the event of an incident.

No sensitive information is expected to be collected during this phase of the project. Only the postal addresses and geographic coordinates of the schools (information that is already public).

5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez
- Pilar Sanz-Cervera

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.2.3 Third-party data restrictions

5.1.2.3.1 Are there any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data?

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Other

The data will provide the map location coordinates of SPED schools. This data is already public.

6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be published in Zenodo once the creation of the maps in HTML format has been completed.

6.1.1.4 Indicate the expected timely release

2024-07-22

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.7 Indicate how the data will be used

The data will be used to contribute results to a scientific article related to the project.

6.1.1.8 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Data will be preserved if:

- a) It can be useful to other researchers interested in the field.
- b) It allows for replication of the results of our project.
- c) It is technically possible to preserve it.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

6.1.2.4 Indicate where the data will be deposited

European Data Portal

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

6.1.2.5 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.2.6 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data.

No specific tools will be necessary to re-use the data.

6.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

Special education schools and special education classrooms in Spain. An analysis of public and private education offerings in Spain (2001-2024)

The data file was compiled using official statistics from the Spanish Ministry of Education: <https://www.educacionfpydeportes.gob.es/en/servicios-al-ciudadano/estadisticas.html>

Information on special education schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools was selected based on their ownership (public, private concerted, or private non concerted) and the autonomous community.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Reuse of Existing Data

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

Secondary data

Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

These data will be stored on two .xls files: one for special education schools and the other one for special education classrooms in mainstream schools.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de facto standard in my discipline

The .xls format does not meet all the requirements to be considered open. However, it is a widely accepted format used by researchers in multiple fields.

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

KB (kilobyte)

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.2 Explain how data provenance will be documented

The provenance of the data will be reported through Zenodo's metadata fields.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

These data will be stored in two .xls files: one for special education schools and the other for special education classrooms in mainstream schools.

Both files will have the same structure: one sheet for each academic year from 2001/2002 to 2023/2024.

The first row will contain the names of the variables to be analyzed.

The first column will be the total number of special education schools (or special education classrooms in mainstream schools).

The following columns will correspond to this figure broken down by school ownership: public, private, or private.

These data will be presented in separate rows for Spain as a whole and for each of the 17 Spanish autonomous communities and cities.

3 Reused Data

3.1 Reused Data

3.1.1 How will existing data be re-used?

To contribute to the wider community (researchers, public authorities, citizen scientists)

<https://www.educacionfpydeportes.gob.es/en/servicios-al-ciudadano/estadisticas.html>

3.1.2 Where can re-used data be found?

The data in this study are an analysis of data previously published by the Spanish Ministry of Education.

The original data can be found here:

<https://www.educacionfpydeportes.gob.es/en/servicios-al-ciudadano/estadisticas.html>

4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident and describe the main risks and how these will be managed

The data will be stored on disco.uv.es, a password-protected digital file storage space provided by the University of Valencia.

The data generated throughout the project will be stored there weekly.

This storage space regularly creates copies of its contents, ensuring that the data can be recovered in the event of an incident.

No sensitive information is expected to be collected during this phase of the project. Only the postal addresses and geographic coordinates of the schools (information that is already public).

5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez
- Pilar Sanz-Cervera

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

The data will be published under license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0.

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.2.3 Third-party data restrictions

5.1.2.3.1 Are there any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data?

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Other

The data will provide information about the number of SPED schools and special education classrooms in mainstream schools during the period 2001/2002 to 2023/2024.

This data is already public. The project will provide the data in an understandable and organized way.

6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be published in Zenodo once the process of its compilation has been completed.

6.1.1.4 Indicate the expected timely release

2025-09-03

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.7 Indicate how the data will be used

The data will be used to contribute results to a scientific article related to the project.

6.1.1.8 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Data will be preserved if:

- a) It can be useful to other researchers interested in the field.
- b) It allows for replication of the results of our project.
- c) It is technically possible to preserve it.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

6.1.2.4 Indicate where the data will be deposited

European Data Portal

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

6.1.2.5 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.2.6 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data.

No specific tools will be necessary to re-use the data.

6.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

Interviews with special education schools professionals

In this phase of the project we will interview teachers, educators, counselors, and members of SPED management teams from the autonomous communities of Catalonia, the Balearic Islands, the Principality of Asturias, and the Valencian Community.

The objective of the interviews will be to understand the perceptions of SPED professionals about how the publication of the additional fourth provision of the LOMLOE (Law on Education and Training) has affected the functioning of their schools so far.

The interviews will be transcribed using Gladia software. The transcripts will be stored on Zenodo as text files.

All interviews will be anonymized.

Only the interviewee's autonomous community of origin will be reported.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Reuse of Existing Data

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

Primary data

Other

Interview transcripts.

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

The data for this phase of the project will be the transcripts of the interviews, presented in text files (one for each interview) in .odt format.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de iure standard in my discipline

Odt files are an open format because they are based on the international OpenDocument Document Format (ODF) standard, a license-free and open-source XML standard that allows documents to be created, edited and shared independently of the software or operating system.

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

MB (megabyte)

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.1 Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced or if third party data are used

The interviews will be recorded using an audio recording device.

They will then be automatically transcribed using Gladia software.

A researcher will review the transcripts, clean them up appropriately, and store them in a text file.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.1 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data

Descriptive

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

A text file will be provided for each interview.

The identity of the interviewees will be completely anonymized.

Each text file will be named according to the professional position held by the interviewee and a consecutive number.

The professional position codes will correspond to the Spanish word for the professional position.

These codes are:

- TUT: Tutor.
- OR: Educational Counselor.
- DIR: Member of the Management Team.
- ED: Special Education Educator.
- AL: Hearing and Language Teacher.
- EF: Physical Education Teacher.
- MUS: Music Teacher.
- FP: Vocational Training Teacher.
- FIS: Physiotherapist.

3 Reused Data

4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident and describe the main risks and how these will be managed

The data will be stored on disco.uv.es, a password-protected digital file storage space provided by the University of Valencia.

The data generated throughout the project will be stored there weekly.

This storage space regularly creates copies of its contents, ensuring that the data can be recovered in the event of an incident.

No sensitive information is expected to be collected during this phase of the project. Only the postal addresses and geographic coordinates of the schools (information that is already public).

5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1.1 Personal data

5.1.1.1 Are there any personal data to be formulated?

No

5.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

- Pilar Sanz-Cervera

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Ethical issues surrounding personal data

All interviews will be anonymized.

Only the interviewee's autonomous community of origin will be reported.

6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be published on Zenodo once the interviews and transcript review are complete.

6.1.1.4 Indicate the expected timely release

2026-06-30

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.7 Indicate how the data will be used

The data will be used to contribute results to a scientific article related to the project.

6.1.1.8 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Data will be preserved if:

- a) It can be useful to other researchers interested in the field.
- b) It allows for replication of the results of our project.
- c) It is technically possible to preserve it.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Other

Interview transcripts.

6.1.2.4 Indicate where the data will be deposited

European Data Portal

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

6.1.2.5 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.2.6 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data.

No specific tools will be necessary to re-use the data.

6.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

Interviews with families of students enrolled in special education schools

In this phase of the project we will interview family members of students enrolled in SPED schools regarding their assessment of the proposals of the Additional Fourth Provision of the LOMLOE (Local Labor Law) and their evaluation of the educational support their children receive in the SPED schools where they are enrolled.

Specifically, we will ask about their impressions regarding academic performance, improvements in autonomy, and attention to students' emotional development provided in the SPED schools, as well as job prospects after completing their SPED education.

The interviews will be transcribed using Gladia software. The transcripts will be stored on Zenodo.

All interviews will be anonymized.

Only the interviewee's autonomous community of origin will be reported.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Reuse of Existing Data

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

Primary data

Other

Interview transcripts.

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

The data for this phase of the project will be the transcripts of the interviews, presented in text files (one for each interview) in .odt format.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de iure standard in my discipline

Odt files are an open format because they are based on the international OpenDocument Document Format (ODF) standard, a license-free and open-source XML standard that allows documents to be created, edited and shared independently of the software or operating system.

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

MB (megabyte)

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.1 Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced or if third party data are used

The interviews will be audio-recorded.

The audio recordings will be transcribed using Gladia.

Each transcript will be reviewed by a member of the research team.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.1 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data

Descriptive

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

A text file will be provided for each interview.

The identity of the interviewees will be completely anonymized.

Each text file will be named according to the autonomous community and a consecutive number.

3 Reused Data

4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident and describe the main risks and how these will be managed

The data will be stored on disco.uv.es, a password-protected digital file storage space provided by the University of Valencia.

The data generated throughout the project will be stored there weekly.

This storage space regularly creates copies of its contents, ensuring that the data can be recovered in the event of an incident.

No sensitive information is expected to be collected during this phase of the project. Only the postal addresses and geographic coordinates of the schools (information that is already public).

5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1.1 Personal data

5.1.1.1 Are there any personal data to be formulated?

No

5.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez
- Pilar Sanz-Cervera

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Ethical issues surrounding personal data

All interviews will be anonymized.

Only the interviewee's autonomous community of origin will be reported.

6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be published on Zenodo once the interviews and transcript review are complete.

6.1.1.4 Indicate the expected timely release

2026-06-30

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.7 Indicate how the data will be used

The data will be used to contribute results to a scientific article related to the project.

6.1.1.8 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Data will be preserved if:

- a) It can be useful to other researchers interested in the field.
- b) It allows for replication of the results of our project.
- c) It is technically possible to preserve it.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Other

Interview transcripts.

6.1.2.4 Indicate where the data will be deposited

European Data Portal

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

6.1.2.5 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.2.6 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data.

No specific tools will be necessary to re-use the data.

6.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

Questionnaires for Professionals

Based on the results of the interviews with professionals, we will design a questionnaire aimed at understanding the perceptions of special education school professionals regarding the changes that the Fourth Additional Provision of the LOMLOE provides for these types of schools.

The results from the questionnaire will be presented in a data sheet.

The content of each item will appear in the first row.

The data will be fully anonymized.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Reuse of Existing Data

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

Primary data

Other

Results of a questionnaire with Likert-type questions.

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

The entire dataset will be contained in a single .xlsx file.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de facto standard in my discipline

The .xlsx format does not meet all the requirements to be considered open. However, it is a widely accepted format used by researchers in multiple fields. Furthermore, the Free Software Foundation considers it a pseudo-standard format, as it complies with the ISO standard.

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

KB (kilobyte)

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.1 Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced or if third party data are used

The questionnaires will be collected using Lime Survey software.

They will then be exported to a spreadsheet.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1 Documentation And Data Quality

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.1 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data

Descriptive

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

The data will be collected using the Lime Survey platform.

This platform creates a new record for each response and allows results to be exported to various spreadsheet formats.

The data will be stored in Zenodo in a single spreadsheet file.

The variable corresponding to the data presented will be indicated in the first row of each column.

If necessary, a .txt text file will be created with additional information about these variables.

3 Reused Data

4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

4.1.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident and describe the main risks and how these will be managed

The data will be collected on the Lime Survey platform, where it will be accessible with a username and password.

A backup of the data collected so far will be made every 15 days.

The responses to the questionnaire will be completely anonymous.

No data or microdata that could identify the person responding will be collected.

5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

5.1.1 Personal data

5.1.1.1 Are there any personal data to be formulated?

No

5.1.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Universidad de Valencia

- Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

- Pilar Sanz-Cervera

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access or restrictions will apply to the data?

Open

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0.

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0.

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Ethical issues surrounding personal data

The responses to the questionnaire will be completely anonymous.

No data or microdata that could identify the person responding will be collected.

6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

Deposit in a FAIR-enabling data repository

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

Once published, Zenodo does not allow records to be deleted.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

The data will be publicly available once the questionnaire collection has been completed and the database has been properly cleaned.

6.1.1.4 Indicate the expected timely release

2026-12-31

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.7 Indicate how the data will be used

The data will be used to contribute results to a scientific article related to the project.

6.1.1.8 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Data will be preserved if:

- a) It can be useful to other researchers interested in the field.
- b) It allows for replication of the results of our project.
- c) It is technically possible to preserve it.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

Other

Questionnaire responses.

6.1.2.4 Indicate where the data will be deposited

European Data Portal

The data will be stored on Zenodo.

6.1.2.5 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.2.6 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data.

No specific tools will be necessary to re-use the data.

6.1.3 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.3.1 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

a. Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

b. Pilar Sanz-Cervera

data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

No cost

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

6. Software Management

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